

POLYETHYLENE/GRAPHENE NANOCOMPOSITES OBTAINED BY SUPPORTED CATALYST OVER FEW GRAPHENE LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

Graphene based materials have great potential to simultaneously improve not only the mechanical and barrier properties but also electrical and thermal conductivities of polymers. The use of graphite and polyolefins as starting materials is convenient because both are inexpensive and with very different properties, one is conductive and the other is insulating, the formation of nanocomposites can extend the applicability of both commodities. In this work we synthesized nanocomposites of polyethylene with two types of graphites, graphite oxide (GO) and reduced graphene oxide (RGO), by *in situ* polymerization using a metallocene catalyst. The GO was obtained through the Staudenmaier oxidation during 24h of natural graphite flakes and the RGO by thermal reduction of GO at 1000°C. Both graphitic materials were formed by few graphene layers, GO had 32.6% of oxygen and RGO had low number of defects, good conductivity and 13.2 % of oxygen. The functional groups were used to support the metallocene catalyst (Cp_2ZrCl_2) with previous treatment with methylaluminoxane (MAO). Both types of nanocomposites were obtained with good catalytic activities, even though, in the case of polyethylene graphite oxide (PEGO) nanocomposites, the catalytic activity decreased with the increase of the amount of GO due to the high quantity of oxygen present that deactivated, in partly, the catalyst. All the nanocomposites showed higher crystallization temperatures (T_c) than the homopolymer, which is very useful in order to decrease the processing cycles. The increase of the glass transition temperatures (T_g) showed an increase of rigidity in the nanocomposites that act as reinforcement of the polymeric matrix, as it can also be seen by the increase in the elastic modulus. All the nanocomposites presented excellent morphology and dispersion. However, the nanocomposites PEGO were insulant while the polyethylene reduced graphene oxide (PERGO) presented a conductivity of $1.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$ with 3.1wt% of RGO.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer/graphite-derived nanocomposites are interesting materials due to their potential conductive properties. Graphite is a commodity and it is found in nature in the form of graphite flakes or powder of various particle sizes. The use of graphite as starting material to produce graphene, or few graphene layers, has grown in importance thanks to Geim and Novoselov studies[1], showing the outstanding electrical and thermal conductivities of graphene. The properties of graphene obtained from graphite are very depended on the exfoliation method. A structured material with a little number of graphene layers and low amount of defects is desirable.

Polyolefin nanocomposites with graphite or graphite oxide (GO) have been prepared, mainly, by blending in the molten state [2-6]. These blending methods have the handicap that nanoparticles are very difficult to disperse. On the other hand, *in situ* polymerization (polymerization of the monomer in the presence of fillers) benefits from the low viscosity of the liquid polymerization media, which also prevents nanoparticle emissions. Dry powder blending with nanoparticles requires special safety precautions and handling procedures to prevent dust explosions, and health hazards resulting from nanoparticle inhalation or absorption [7]. However, *in situ* polymerization of ethylene or propylene with graphite or graphite-derived materials has been less studied.

In recent years our research group has been working to obtain graphene/polyolefin nanocomposites using *in situ* polymerization with metallocene catalysts [8-12]. Our results show improvement on the Young modulus, crystallization temperature, thermal stability, and conductivity in the nanocomposites compared with neat polymer; however, our electrical percolation threshold was still too high. Those previous results were obtained using commercially expanded graphite sonicated during 8 h, by *in situ* polymerization using a no covalent approach. However, in many cases, to achieve stable dispersions of graphene and adequate control of the microstructure of the nanocomposites, covalent functionalization of graphene with polymers may be necessary [13, 14].

In the present work, there were prepared graphite oxide (GO) from natural graphite flakes by oxidation during 24h using the Staudenmaier [15] and reduced graphite oxide (RGO) by thermal reduction of GO at 1000°C. The objective was to immobilize metallocene catalyst on graphene impregnated by methylaluminumoxane (MAO) using the oxygen functional groups of the fillers and thus growing the polyolefin from the graphene surface. The focus was to improve graphene exfoliation in the polymeric matrix and consequently improve the nanocomposite properties. The properties of the nanocomposites already obtained by the no covalent technique were compared with those obtained by the covalent approach. The ultimate goal, in this study, was to obtain a conductive material with high processability and good stiffness-to-density ratios so that it can be used in electronic devices for transducers, low-temperature heaters, cellular cells, and also in the aerospace and automotive industries.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

GO was synthesized from flakes using a modified Staudenmaier method [15], where the time of oxidation used was 24 h. The GO was then heated at 1000 °C for 30 s in an oven, using a closed quartz ampoule with normal atmosphere obtaining reduced graphite oxide (RGO).

For catalyst support, GO or RGO were placed in a Schlenk vessel with toluene using inert atmosphere and sonicated during 8 h in an ultrasound bath working at 40 kHz. The amount of GO and RGO used varied between 100 to 1000 mg. Then, 15 wt.% MAO was added to the graphite suspension and sonicated for additional 30 min. Next, Cp_2ZrCl_2 was added in an amount of 2 wt.% Zr/GO or Zr/RGO, left another 30 min in the ultrasonic bath, and 2 h with stirring at 50 °C. The supernatant was then decanted and the solid washed three times with toluene. Thereafter, the GO/MAO/ Cp_2ZrCl_2 or RGO/MAO/ Cp_2ZrCl_2 was used as the catalyst for the polymerization of ethylene.

Polymerization reactions were performed in a 100-ml reactor; toluene was used as the solvent and MAO as the co-catalyst (Al/Zr=100). The reactions were performed at 70 °C using a 3.0-bar ethylene pressure for 30 min. The polymerization reactions were stopped using ethanol acidified with HCl (10%).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The graphite oxide (GO) obtained by the Staudenmaier method of oxidation but using 24h instead of 96h and the subsequently thermal reduced graphite oxide (RGO) were extensively characterized. Elementary analysis showed the oxidation of the graphite flakes (starting material) in GO where the amount of oxygen was 32.6 % and the reduction of GO to RGO where the oxygen decreased to 13.2 %. X-ray diffraction (XRD) showed the exfoliation of graphite which crystal size was reduced from 17 nm (Flake) to 10 nm in GO and finally to 5 nm for RGO. The oxygen functional groups help to separate the graphene sheets increasing the exfoliation. Raman spectroscopy showed the recuperation

of the graphitic structure in RGO where the presence of defects quantified by I_D/I_G was close to the graphite of departure. Finally the conductivity decrease in GO due to the high amount of oxygen functional groups that act as defects of the graphitic structure. On the other hand conductivity was increased in RGO, even compared with the starting flakes, due to the restoration of the graphitic structure and also the higher exfoliation of this material. All this data is shown in Table 1.

Sample	C (%) (CHN)	O (%) (CHN)	2 θ ($^\circ$) (XRD)	d (nm) (XRD)	C(nm) (XRD)	Conductividade (S.cm ⁻¹)	I_D/I_G (Raman)
Flake	99.6 ^a	-	26.55	0.33	17	6.02×10^{-2}	0.7
GO	64.6	32.6	11.10	0.80	10	1.15×10^{-2}	- ^b
RGO	86.3	13.2	25.71	0.35	5	1.73×10^{-1}	0.8

^a Technical information from the manufacturer ^b It was not possible to calculate

Table 1: Characterization of the starting material (Flake) and the obtained graphites GO and RGO.

Scanning and transmission electronic microscopies (Fig. 1) confirm that the reduced graphite oxide obtained is constituted by few graphene layers.

Figure 1: a) SEM of RGO and b) TEM of RGO.

GO and RGO impregnated with methylaluminoxane (MAO) were used to support the catalyst Cp_2ZrCl_2 . The contents of zirconium fixed on the nanoparticles were determined by inductively coupled plasma emission spectroscopy (ICP). Initially there were placed 2 wt% of Zr over the support and the amount fixed were 1.31 wt.% for Zr/GO and 0.36 wt.% for Zr/RGO, this is in accordance with the oxygen content of each support that is the atom where the catalytic system is bonded.

Polyethylene nanocomposites were obtained by polymerization of ethylene over the prepared supported catalytic systems ($Cp_2ZrCl_2/MAO/GO$ and $Cp_2ZrCl_2/MAO/RGO$). The catalytic activities are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that when GO was used the catalytic activities decreased with the increase in the amount of GO, probably due to the high number of oxygen groups in this support that can deactivate the catalyst. On the other hand, when RGO was used the decrease in the catalytic activities was less significant and this in accord to the lower number of functional oxygen groups in this support. The existence of some oxygen atoms on the graphite is necessary to help in the fixation of the catalyst. Crystallization temperatures (Tab. 2) of the nanocomposites were, in general, 2-4 $^\circ C$

higher than those of the neat PE, showing the nucleation power of the filler. Glass transition temperatures were also slightly superior in the nanocomposites than in PE, showing an increase in rigidity. Elastic moduli at 25°C were all higher in the nanocomposites compared to PE showing the reinforcement effect of the fillers. The nanocomposites of polyethylene with GO (PEGO) were not conductive, even when it was used 9.5 wt. % of GO. This is probably due to the high number of defect in the graphitic structure of GO represented by 32.6 % of oxygen. On the other hand the presence of RGO in PE increased the electrical conductivity to a value of $1.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$ with only 3.1 wt. % of filler in PE, even if there was still 13.2 % of oxygen in the graphite used. This conductivity is superior to the obtained, previously, with the same amount of graphite by in situ polymerization of ethylene with a non-supported system [11].

Samples	Filler (wt.%)	Catalytic Activity (KgPE/n _{Zr} .h.atm)	Tc (°C)	Tg (°C)	E' 25°C (MPa)	σ (S.cm ⁻¹)
PE	0.0	166	116	-113.2	1178	
PEGO1	1.1	415	118	111.1	1553	
PEGO2	2.5	187	117	-111.6	2082	
PEGO3	3.0	153	118			
PEGO4	9.5	49	115	-111.7	2313	1.5×10^{-12}
PERGO1	2.2	780	119	-111.5	2097	8.5×10^{-8}
PERGO2	3.1	544	120			$1,1 \times 10^{-5}$
PERGO3	3.3	518	120	-112.6	2288	
PERGO4	3.7	438	120	-111.5	2024	

σ = Electrical conductivity

Table 2: Nanocomposites of PE with GO and RGO.

Fig. 2 shows the SEM of the PEGO and PERGO nanocomposites with similar amount of fillers (2.5 and 2.2 %, respectively). The nanocomposites are formed by spherical like particles that flow easily, preventing the fouling of the reactor. The morphologies are different, the PERGO is formed by layered blades of graphite recovered PE more ordered than the PEGO ones.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: MEV of nanocomposites: PEGO2 (a) and PERGO1 (b).

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two types of graphite, graphite oxide (GO) and reduced graphite oxide (RGO) obtained from graphite flakes were used as filler of polyethylene nanocomposites. GO had 32.6 % of oxygen and RGO 13.2%, those functional groups were used to impregnate methylaluminoxane over the support and to help in the exfoliation of the graphite. These fillers were used to support the catalyst, Cp_2ZrCl_2 and to obtain nanocomposites by in situ polymerization. The resulting nanocomposites replied the morphology of the supported catalyst systems. Their properties were very influenced by the type of graphite. In both cases the exfoliated graphite acted as reinforcement. The nanocomposites obtained with GO were insulant while the ones with RGO presented the electrical properties of a semiconductor. The results of conductivity obtained with the supported catalyst over RGO were superior to the obtained when the non-covalent method was used in the *in situ* polymerization.

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